

IMPERFECT UTOPIAS

Is your shared utopian future really perfect...

Or is it not?

Beyond Opposition

These comics are devised from a workshop by **Culture Junction** and **Beyond Opposition**, with special thanks to the participants who took part.

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Think about where you share space with people who **fundamentally disagree** with you on gender, sexuality, and abortion.

A coffee shop

A shared office space

A public street

How do you **engage** with other people if they express positions that you fundamentally disagree with **in those spaces**? Do you...

listen?

walk away?

ask them to leave?

protest them?

try to change their mind?

When thinking about these disagreements and oppositions around gender, sexuality, and/or abortion, what utopian future do you want to see?

In this utopian future, how would you share space with the people who fundamentally disagree with you on gender, sexuality and/or abortion?

During the workshop in Glasgow, participants were put into groups and asked to work together to imagine a utopian future that they could share together while still holding their different positions on gender, sexuality and abortion.

The groups were given a script and asked to devise a short piece of theatre where they encountered each other and a mystery group of other people.

If you were given **this script**, who would you be speaking to? How would **you interact** with the other character and the others who disagree with you...?

BEYOND OPPOSITION

You: Hi

Them: Hi

You: What do you think?

Them: What do you think?

You: Well...

Them: I think...

You: It's perfect

Them: Perfect... even though it's not

You: They're still here

Them: They are

You: ...Yeah

Them: ...Yeah

You: ...but it's ...perfect

Them: Yeah... perfect

Is your shared utopian future really perfect...

Or is it not?

We now invite you to enter into three of the shared utopias imagined by our participants.

Reflecting on the future you want to see in relation to gender, sexuality and abortion, ***how do you feel about these spaces?***

the FANTASY

FRANCISCA
asexual,
ex-trans ally
with concerns

CAROL
bisexual
christian,
supports
trans rights

SOPHIE
gender
critical
lesbian

SOMEWHERE IN THE CLOUDS...

the PUB

PATRICK
gay leftist
cis man

SIOBHAN
queer feminist
cis woman

YOUR LOCAL PUB IS A PLACE WHERE PEOPLE LEAVE THEIR PREJUDICES AT THE DOOR AND MIGHT HAVE A LAUGH OVER THEIR OPINIONS AND JOKE. THERE'S SOMETHING ABOUT THE LOCAL PUB THAT MAKES THIS CRUCIAL.

THE

IMPASSE

CAROL

bisexual
woman, wife
and parent

FRANCISCA

asexual woman
looking for
middle ground

GEORGE

agender, old
fashioned left
winger

I DON'T WANT TO SPEAK FOR THE OTHERS--SO JUST CORRECT ME IF I'M WRONG--

BUT I THINK WE ALL REALISED THAT FOR IT TO BE A "PERFECT FUTURE" ONE OF US WOULD HAVE TO NOT BE THERE.

I THINK WE POSSIBLY FELT THE THREE OF US...

COULDN'T COEXIST IN THIS PLACE.

IT'S
PERFECTLY
AWFUL.

Not everyone wants the same future.

If we accept that we cannot change everyone's minds on issues relating to gender, sexuality, and abortion...

and we accept that we will still have to share space with people we fundamentally disagree with on those issues...

what future spaces do we need to create together to coexist beyond opposition?

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This publication is part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. (Grant agreement No. 817897)

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project name: **Beyond Opposition: Opposing Sexual and Gender Rights, Transforming Everyday Spaces**

For more information, visit beyondopposition.org

What utopian future do you want to see?

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